

The Chemistry of Grandifoline, a Bisindole Alkaloid*

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It is a privilege and a great honour for me to deliver the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture today in the Convention of Chemists which is being held under the joint auspices of the Indian Chemical Society and the Chemical Research Committee of the C.S.I.R (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India). I take this opportunity to express my sincere thanks to the President and members of the Indian Chemical Society for selecting me as Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecturer. I will speak on this occasion on the chemistry of Grandifoline—a Bis Indole Alkaloid of *Voacanga grandifolia*. At the onset, I should like to pay my homage to my revered teacher, Acharya P. C. Ray. Although his field of specialisation was Inorganic Chemistry he made significant contributions on Organic sulphur compounds specially on "Mercaptans" and on the "Chemistry of Natural Products".

Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray is one of the towering personalities who was born in the nineteenth century in Khulna district, now in Bangladesh. Although renowned as an educationist and a researcher he contributed in no small measure in preparing the ground for the emergence of modern Bengal viz. intellectual regeneration, industrial development, social reform, economic freedom, employment for the people and political advancement of the country. Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works was the first industrial venture of Acharya Ray. He did not live to see the changing pattern of India's economy. Had he lived in the post-independence period, he would have taken a deeper plunge into the unknown than many balance-sheet minded industrialists. To him the Bengal Chemical was something more than a dividend-earning venture. It stood for him as a symbol of the growing self-respect of his people and of his confidence in the destiny of the country. Unfortunately he had to disagree with the management towards the end of his life. He was also associated with many other ventures, but Bengal Chemical was his "first love".

Acharya Ray was an advocator of drugs obtained from medicinal herbs. Extracts of Kalmegh (*Andrographis paniculata*), Kurchi (*Holarrhena antidysenterica*), Syrup of Vasaka (*Adhatoda vasica*), Aqua Ptychotis (Ajowun water) are a few of the several indigenous preparations which competed

against Western drugs and gained popularity in the Indian market and still find use for the treatment of various ailments.

Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works, Calcutta, a pioneering Pharmaceutical concern in India, produced several galenical preparations of medicinal herbs which were prescribed by the then reputed doctors, Sir Nilratan Sarker and Sri U. N. Brahmachari. Acharya Ray's work on the chemistry of onion and garlic in those days when isolation techniques were most primitive, is indeed commendable. Incidentally, I would like to mention that garlic possesses insecticidal and antiarthritis properties and its extract is being exported under the name "Lawsoona".

I came in close association with Acharya P. C. Ray when I was a post-graduate student in the University College of Science. He inspired me to study the chemistry of Natural Products and to utilise these resources for the benefit of the "Common Man". Many of them are being used as such or they are being used as intermediates for the production of medicinal or other useful products.

Today's lecture therefore has relevance to the work of Acharya Ray. Before entering into the main subject I would like to tell you briefly the reason for selecting this particular topic. Although we have been engaged in the studies on the chemistry, pharmacology and clinical experiments of terpenoids, polyphenolics and nitrogen heterocycles, research in the field of indole alkaloids has been a major and continuing interest in our laboratory¹ as early as mid-thirties mainly because of their physiological and medicinal significance in addition to their fascinating structures. Some of the interesting indole compounds will be shown in this connection.

(A) Tryptophan

(B) Tryptamine

It would be appropriate to mention some of the indole-derived active substances.

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Biologically and Medicinally Interesting Monomeric Indole Compounds

Compound 1	Structure 2	Biological Activity 3
1. 5-Hydroxy tryptamine (Serotonin)		Vasoconstrictor ³ , regulates gastric secretion and intestinal peristalsis; Disruption in Serotonin levels is considered to be one of the causes of behavioral disorder.
2. N-Acetyl-methylserotonin (Melatonin, Hormone of Pineal gland)		It plays the role in controlling ³ diurnal variations in biological functions.
3. LSD ; Lysergic acid diethyl amide		Psychotomimetic activity ⁴ (Hallucinogen)
4. Luciferin (<i>Cypridina hilgendorfi</i>)		Responsible for light emission ⁵ (Photobiology)
5. Glucobrassicin (Cabbage, <i>Brassica oleracea</i>)		Bound Ascorbic acid ⁶ (Indole conjugate)
6. Ascorbigen A R=α-OH		Indole-3-aldehyde ⁷ , conjugate of Ascorbic acid
7. Ascorbigen B R=β-OH		Indole conjugate of Ascorbic acid ⁸ source of Vitamin C.
8. δ-Yohimbine (Ajmalicine), <i>Rauwolfia canescens</i> & <i>Vinca rosea</i> (<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>)		Treatment of Angina and peripheral vasodilator ⁹ .

Compound 1	Structure 2	Biological activity 3
9. Reserpine		Tranquilliser*

Since mid 1930's my research colleagues have isolated more than 30 new monomeric indole alkaloids from various species of Apocynaceae, Rubiaceae, Loganiaceae and Rutaceae of which nareline¹⁰ isolated from *Alstonia scholaris*, is one of the recent and exciting members. The structure elucidation of nareline has opened a new chapter in the chemistry of indole alkaloids.

Besides monomeric indolic bases we have also isolated a number of bis-indolic compounds (or dimeric indole alkaloids as they are commonly called) from Apocynaceous species. Though nearly eighty such compounds have been reported to-date,

the structure elucidation goes back to twelve years only. This fact clearly demonstrates that without the recent rapid development of separation and analytical techniques, particularly CMR & PMR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry and X-ray analysis, this special field would have remained virtually unopened. Besides academic importance bis-indole alkaloids are of paramount interest because of the specific pharmacological properties such as the muscle relaxation-action of the curare alkaloids, for which these find applications in surgery. The anti-leukemic activity of the Vinca alkaloids is also well known. Several biologically active dimeric indole alkaloids are presented below in this connection.

Biologically Active Bis Indole Alkaloids

10. C-Toxiferine (Loganiaceae, *Strychnos toxifera* F. Schomb, *S. subcordata* spruce)

C-Toxiferine¹¹ is the most active and specific curarising agent for man and of longest paralytic activity. It has a powerful neuromuscular blocking activity. It is therefore specially suited for use in surgical operations of long duration and in the treatment of tetanus. Side effect of circulation or respiration (broncho constriction) has never been observed.

11. Vincalokoblastine (Vinblastine, VLB)

12, 18

R₁ = -Me; R₂ = -OMe;
R₃ = -COMe; R₄ = -CO₂Me

12. Vincristine

R₁ = -CHO; R₂ = -OMe; R₃ = -COMe;
R₄ = -CO₂Me

In the treatment of choriocarcinoma, certain forms of leukemia and Hodgkin's disease.

Bis-Indole Alkaloids isolated from Alstonia macrophylla^{1,4,15}

13. Villalstonine

14. Macralstonine

15. Macralstonidine

Monomeric indole compounds containing C₁₀ or C₁₁ units in the nitrogenous moiety are synthesised in nature from tryptophan or its biochemical equivalent, tryptamine. Tryptamine on cyclisation at C₂ followed by oxidative coupling at C₃ generates the dimer chimonanthe^{1,5a}.

Chimonanthe

Recently we have isolated two dimeric indole bases from *Voacanga grandifolia* (Apocynaceae). One of these is vobtusine already known in the literature and the other is a new compound and has been designated grandifoline.

Difficulties which have been encountered with the bis-indole alkaloids of the vobtusine type in connection with their structure determination are owing to the obstinacy of these alkaloids to undergo cleavage to the monomeric constituents in contrast to the dimers occurring in *Strychnos* and *Vinca* species. To-date no bis-indole alkaloids related to vobtusine have been found to break up into their monomers. The nmr and mass spectra are so complex that the structural interpretation of the fragments is rather difficult. The nature of the coupling between the two monomeric components is not easy to ascertain.

Since grandifoline, the bis-indole alkaloid of *V. grandifolia*, is structurally related to vobtusine¹⁶ it would be pertinent to discuss the structure of vobtusine. The information available therefrom would help to correlate grandifoline with vobtusine and its epimer isovobtusine.

Vobtusine has been isolated on various occasions from different apocynaceous species since early fifty's. However its structure(I) was proposed in 1966 mainly on the basis of its UV, IR, PMR and Mass spectra without any correct assignment of the configuration at various chiral centres. Structure(I) was subsequently modified with minor changes from X-ray analysis of its dibromo-derivative.

The molecular formula of vobtusine (C₄₃H₅₀O₆N₄) could be established from high resolution mass spectrometry. Different functionalities in the molecule could be ascertained mainly from spectral studies. The ultraviolet and infrared spectra revealed the presence of an α -methylene indole chromophore occurring as a methyl β -anilino-acrylate(II). This observation was quite consistent with the high optical rotation of the compound.

(I) Vobtusine

(II) Methyl- β -anilinoacrylate

(III) Vincadifformine

(IIIa) Decarbomethoxy-vincadifformine (Indolenine)

Further analysis of the electronic spectra of vobtusine showed that the spectra corresponded to the summation effect of two different chromophores viz. carbomethoxy- α -methyleneindoline (β -anilino acrylic ester)(II) and N-alkyl-7-alkoxy indoline(IV). This could be substantiated from the subtraction spectra of vobtusine and vincadifformine(III)¹⁷.

This infers that vobtusine contains two indole nuclei having different environments. This clearly demonstrates that this alkaloid is a dimeric indolic base.

The presence of aromatic methoxyl, -NH, -OH in vobtusine was apparent from the IR, PMR and -mass spectra. The tertiary nature of the hydroxyl was revealed from the failure of the compound to undergo acylation, from its facile dehydration in the mass spectrometer and its conversion to an anhydroderivative, $C_{43}H_{48}N_4O_5$ (V), on mild acid treatment of the base with aq. HCl. Interestingly the anhydrobase retained the β -anilino acrylic ester moiety. Energetic reaction with dilute HCl or HBr in acetic acid vobtusine afforded decarbomethoxyanhydrovobtusine, $C_{41}H_{46}N_4O_3$ (VI) which like vincadifformine(III) showed strong IR absorption for $>C=N$ grouping (indolenine group).

The UV spectrum of anhydrovobtusine is a summation of vincadifformine(III) and 2-methylene-7-methoxy indoline chromophore. The occurrence of the oxygen atoms as ether linkages was subsequently revealed from their inert character. These ether linkages are found to be resistant to LAH and Zn/hot sulphuric acid treatment. One of the monomers could be recognised as vincadifformine(III). The other moiety was settled as aspidospermine involving the chromophore N-alkyl-7-alkoxyindoline(VIII) from mass spectrometric investigation. This fact could decide the mode of linkage of two monomers in vobtusine. The structure thus emerged out was later substantiated from X-ray analysis and CMR spectra of the compound which revealed that two monomeric units are united through a spiran linkage.

(IV) N-alkyl-7-alkoxy indoline

(V) Anhydrovobtusine

(VI) Decarbomethoxyanhydrovobtusine

The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of vobtusine is elaborated :

¹³C-NMR Spectra of Vobtusine¹⁸

X-ray analysis of the dibromo derivative of vobtusine proved unambiguously that vobtusine should have a bis-indole structure. The molecular

framework is composed of a spiro system involving vandrikinine like skeleton (VIIb) having a C₁ unit (attached to N_a) through which the second monomer is linked up (I).

(VIIa) Y=H
(VIIb) Y=OMe, Vandrikinine¹⁹

(VIII) Tabersonine¹⁹

However CMR spectra were useful in structure determination of vobtusine. In fact a complete assignment for all the carbons of vobtusine could be achieved from the studies of the ¹³C NMR spectra of the compound and the comparison of the spectra with those of the aspidosperma bases²⁰ like

Vobtusine and its isomer isovobtusine differ from each other only in the configuration at C-14. The CMR spectra which had been successfully employed to distinguish between these two stereoisomers at C₁₄ are presented in Table 2 :

The following general comment could be made on the basis of the carbon shift difference data cited in the table along with other compounds varying at C-14 carbon centre. In agreement with these observations on quaternary carbon shifts, the values of the spiro carbon which is common to two monomer units of the bis-indoline alkaloids suffers only minor perturbation from the normal to the 14-iso series.

TABLE 1—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF VOBTUSINE, VANDRIKINE AND TABERSONINE

	Tabersonine ^d	Vobtusine ^e		Vandrikinine ^e	Vobtusine ^e
C-2	166.7	166.6	C-2'	167.4	99.7
C-3	50.3 ^a	53.7	C-3'	45.7	48.7
C-5	50.8 ^a	50.9	C-5'	51.2	59.1
C-6	44.3	44.9	C-6'	45.1	31.1
C-7	55.0	54.8	C-7'	54.2	55.9
C-8	137.8	137.6	C-8'	130.5	134.2
C-9	121.4	121.2	C-9'	121.5	114.5
C-10	120.5	120.4	C-10'	104.8	118.1
C-11	127.6	127.4	C-11'	159.8	110.8
C-12	109.2	109.1	C-12'	96.5	144.9
C-13	143.1	142.8	C-13'	144.1	137.2
C-14	124.8	39.6	C-14'	27.4 ^c	25.7
C-15	132.9	87.4	C-15'	79.8	80.3
C-16	92.2	94.3	C-16'	93.9	31.5
C-17	26.7 ^b	27.3	C-17'	26.6 ^c	32.4
C-18	7.3	64.2	C-18'	64.7	65.1
C-19	28.4 ^b	34.8	C-19'	34.6	36.6
C-20	41.2	47.6	C-20'	46.4	44.1
C-21	69.9	68.9	C-21'	68.7	63.6
C=O	168.8	168.3	C-22'		34.1
-OCH ₃	50.8	50.9	C-23'		46.1
			Ar-OCH ₃		55.0
			C=O	168.5	
			O		
			-C-OCH ₃	50.8	

'a', 'b', 'c' Values may be interchanged.
'd' : (TMS)=(CHCl₃)+77.2 ppm.
'e' : (TMS)=(CDCl₃)+76.9 ppm.

vandrikinine(VIIb) and tabersonine(VIII). All the carbon signals of these compounds including vobtusine are listed in Table 1.

Correct evidence for the spiran linkage and the information on chirality at this linkage has been procured from its CMR spectra.

(I) Vobtusine

(Ia) Isovobtusine

TABLE 2—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFT DIFFERENCES INDICATIVE OF C-14 CONFIGURATION

	Vobtusine	Δ	Isovobtusine
C-3	53.7		58.0
C-14	39.6		38.9
C-15	87.4		81.5
C-18	64.2		63.7
C-16'	31.5		32.4
C-22'	34.1		35.1
C-23'	46.1		46.5
C-3		+ 4.3	
C-14		- 0.7	
C-15		- 5.9	
C-18		- 0.5	
C-16'		+ 0.9	
C-22'		+ 1.0	
C-23'		+ 0.4	

Δ=(iso)-(normal) in ppm.

From a consideration of all the spectra conjointly viz. the ^{13}C -NMR spectra with the cracking pattern observed in the mass spectra, ^1H nmr spectrum and other molecular spectra, the structure of vobtusine and its stereochemistry could be unambiguously settled.

The structure of vobtusine was subsequently confirmed by X-ray diffraction studies.

Now the relationship between grandifoline and vobtusine would be discussed. Grandifoline, $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{48}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$, the bis-indole alkaloid of vobtusine type, with an additional ring system was isolated in our laboratory as early as 1960's as a minor constituent from the leaves of *Voacanga grandifolia* (Miq.) Rolfe collected from Indian Botanic Garden, Shibpur, Howrah. The same compound was later isolated from the leaves of *V. africana* Stampf and *V. thoursii* Roem et Schult, from the leaves and stems of *Callichillia sessilis*²¹ and the root bark of *Hedranthera barteri* (Hook. f.) Pichon. The structure elucidation of grandifoline with all its stereochemical implications will now be discussed.

Grandifoline could be isolated from the petrol and chloroform extracts of the plant *V. grandifolia* following the usual procedure. It crystallised from petrol ether : benzene (4 : 1) mixture in fine needles, showing the m.p. 238° . It was found to be strongly laevorotatory in nature having high rotation $[\alpha]_D^{25} -225^\circ$ (CHCl_3) and displayed characteristic colour reactions for alkaloids, e.g., it gave ultramarine blue color with ceric ammonium sulphate. The molecular formula $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{48}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ was assigned to the compound on the basis of elemental analyses and high resolution mass spectrum which showed a single molecular ion peak at m/e 716.3574.

The electronic spectra of grandifoline in the UV region showed absorption maxima at $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ ($\log \epsilon$) : 223 (4.53), 263 (4.05), 302 (4.14) and 326 (4.20) nm. A comparative study of the UV data with those of various indole and dihydroindole alkaloids having characteristic chromophoric systems suggested that the spectrum is the summation effect of two different chromophores viz. 7-alkoxy N-alkyl dihydroindole(IV) system and a β -anilino methylacrylic ester(II) moiety. These two chromophores were also characteristic of vobtusine itself and in fact, the UV spectra of vobtusine and grandifoline were indistinguishable.

The presence of the above two chromophores could be substantiated by the differential UV spectrum of grandifoline with (-) echitovenine²² (IX) which was almost superimposable with that of N₂-ethyl desacetyl aspidospermidine(X). This revealed the presence of two indole moieties in

grandifoline thereby confirming the bis-indole structure of this alkaloid.

(IX) (-) Echitovenine

(X) N₂ ethyl desacetyl aspidospermidine

The UV spectrum of grandifoline was found to be identical with that of anhydrovobtusine when the spectrum was run for 2-2.5 hrs after addition of conc. HCl to the original compound. The presence of an -NH moiety and a β -anilino acrylic ester grouping in the molecule was disclosed from its IR spectrum which showed the corresponding peaks at 3401 and 1684 & 1613 cm^{-1} respectively. The peaks corresponding to the β -anilino acrylate system in the IR spectrum along with other peaks confirmed the presence of the group(II) in the molecule of grandifoline. The IR spectra of vobtusine and grandifoline were found to be identical in the region 1400-4000 cm^{-1} further indicating that the two substances must possess the same or nearly the same structural pattern.

It was however interesting to observe that the mass spectral fragmentation pattern of grandifoline was practically the same as that of vobtusine. This would be discussed later. It was therefore apparent that in all probability, the gross skeleton of grandifoline is the same as that of vobtusine. Accepting this as a working hypothesis, the NMR spectra will be examined and also appropriate transformation reactions that have been carried out, will be elaborated to confirm this view.

The PMR spectrum of the compound disclosed the presence of an -NH function (δ 8.98, s), an aromatic methoxyl (δ 3.78, s) and an ester methyl (δ 3.76, s) in the molecule. The 9-H resonated at δ 7.55 as a doublet with fine splitting ($J=8$ Hz) which was further confirmed by decoupling experiments. The other six aromatic protons were traced as a multiplet ca. δ 6.5-7.4 indicating that the two monomers were not joined through the aromatic nuclei. A singlet at δ 4.18 accounted for one proton corresponding either to 21'-H or 15-H.

The C₃-H which is flanked between one nitrogen and one oxygen atom resonated as another singlet at δ 4.75. The PMR spectrum of vobtusine(I) showed a doublet at δ 5.13 ($J=1+$ Hz) due to the geminal coupling of the two protons at C-23'. This peak was also found to be present in grandifoline which also supported the fact that the ether bridge had not been formed between C-2' and C-23', i.e.,

the possibility of the formulation (XI) for grandifoline is excluded.

(XI) Grandifoline

A careful analysis of the molecular formula of grandifoline ($C_{43}H_{48}N_4O_6$) revealed that it contained two hydrogens less than vobtusine ($C_{43}H_{50}N_4O_6$). A comparative study of their spectral data (UV, IR, NMR and MS) of these two indolic compounds further disclosed their similarity, and these two alkaloids have identical or very similar molecular architecture thereby suggesting that grandifoline must contain either :

- (i) one more double bond than vobtusine,
- or (ii) one more ring than vobtusine,
- or (iii) a ketone function instead of a hydroxyl group,
- or (iv) an ether bridge instead of hydroxyl group.

A clear insight into the molecular geometry of grandifoline was obtained from a thorough inspection of its mass spectrum and subsequent correlation with vobtusine. Before going into the details of the cracking pattern of grandifoline, it is intended to discuss the mass spectral fragmentation of vobtusine itself as the mass spectra of the two compounds are very much interrelated.

The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of grandifoline and that of vobtusine are essentially the same. In its mass spectrum, vobtusine registered significant peaks at m/e 718 (M^+), 660, 504, 393, 363, 305, 188, 174, 138 and 110. Grandifoline offered the corresponding peaks at m/e 716 (M^+), 658, 502, 391 which were 2 μ less than vobtusine while the remaining peaks, i.e., m/e 363, 305, 188, 174, 138 and 110 remained unaltered. This result simply led to the conclusion that grandifoline must be dehydrovobtusine. Treatment of vobtusine with CH_3OD

led to the introduction of 2 deuterium atoms in the molecule as shown by its molecular ion peak at m/e 720 while in grandifoline only one proton was exchanged by deuterium under the same condition (M^+ 717). The peaks at m/e 363 and 305 of grandifoline were shifted by one mass unit in the corresponding D_1 -derivative simply showing that the deuteration occurred in the 'A' part of the molecule and grandifoline must be lacking the 2'-OH group of vobtusine in its original form.

The spectral analysis was useful in providing valuable information. The IR spectrum of grandifoline precludes the possibility of the presence of any 5-membered or 6-membered lactone ring in the molecule, its UV spectrum indicated the absence of an N_α -acyl moiety. Considering these data it could be concluded that the 2'-OH group of vobtusine must be present in grandifoline in the form of an ether bridge.

Grandifoline when heated with 70% H_3PO_4 at 200° was cleaved to a monomer, 1,2-dehydrobeninine^{2a} (XII) along with 3 moles of formaldehyde. The compound was identified by spectroscopic analyses.

(XII) 1, 2 Dehydrobeninine

Incidentally, this is the first report of the cleavage of a vobtusine-type alkaloid in contrast to other bisindole alkaloids, e.g., voacamine and vinblastine groups.

A few reactions were carried out on grandifoline to confirm its structure. Catalytic reduction of the compound with H_2 in presence of platinum in 10% $MeOH-CH_3COOH$ afforded dihydrograndifoline, $C_{43}H_{50}N_4O_6$ (M^+ 718), which was isomeric with vobtusine. $NaBH_4$ reduction of grandifoline in $MeOH$ also resulted in the isolation of the same product. Dihydrograndifoline imparted a red-blue color with CaS . Vobtusine and dihydrograndifoline showed identical UV and IR spectra indicating that the two compounds are either same or very much structurally related.

The signals at δ 7.55, 4.75 and 4.18 present in the grandifoline were also discernible in the PMR spectrum of dihydrograndifoline. Another doublet at δ 4.70 ($J=14$ Hz) could be traced in its PMR spectrum corresponding to one at δ 5.13 found in both grandifoline and vobtusine. The mass spectrum of dihydrograndifoline, which registered the same

molecular ion peak at m/e 718, showed important peaks at m/e 700 ($M^+ - 18$), 660 ($M^+ - \text{COOCH}_3$), 642 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{COOCH}_3$), 504, 393, 305, 149, 138 and 110, which were also present in the mass spectrum of vobtusine.

Reduction of grandifoline with NaBD_4 in CH_3OD afforded monodeuterated dihydrograndifoline, $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{45}\text{D}_1\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ ($M^+ 719$). In the mass spectrum of the D_1 -dihydrograndifoline, the peaks at m/e 700, 660, 642, 504 and 393 present in the original compound were shifted by 1 mu. It therefore followed that in dihydrograndifoline, the hydroxyl group must be at C-2', as observed in all vobtusine derivatives.

As grandifoline itself does not contain any hydroxyl group, the 2'-OH group present in dihydrograndifoline must be involved as an ether bridge in the parent compound.

Vobtusine is well known to produce the corresponding anhydroderivative in presence of mineral acid. Similarly, when dihydrograndifoline was treated with 6(N) H_2SO_4 at 25° for 15 hrs, it afforded dihydroanhydrograndifoline, $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{45}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5$ ($M^+ 700$). This compound gave a green color with CAS and was found to be isomeric with anhydrovobtusine. The spectral data (UV, IR, NMR and MS) of dihydroanhydrograndifoline were almost similar to anhydrovobtusine. D_1 -dihydroanhydrograndifoline could be prepared by similar acid treatment of D_1 -dihydrograndifoline. In its mass spectrum, the major peaks at m/e 701, 643, 563, 505, 487, 306, 305 and 138 were observed. Subsequently, dihydroanhydrograndifoline was found to be identical with owerreine (XIII), a new bisindole alkaloid isolated from *Hedranthera barteri* and it had been proved unambiguously that owerreine belonged to the series having 14-isovobtusine skeleton. Dihydroanhydrograndifoline showed $[\alpha]_D$ in CHCl_3 , $-496 \pm 10^\circ$ while the corresponding value of owerreine in the same solvent is $-473 \pm 8^\circ$.

(XIII) Owerreine = Dihydroanhydrograndifoline

When grandifoline was refluxed at 80° with 0.01(N) HCl in 50% dioxan for 2 hrs, it formed

grandifoline diol (XIV). In the spectral analyses this diol confirmed the presence of $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{NH}$ and β -anilino acrylic ester groups. Surprisingly the UV spectrum of grandifoline diol was identical to that of vobtusine.

(XIV) Grandifolinediol

In the PMR spectrum of grandifolinediol, a singlet at δ 8.98 was observed and this was attributed to an $-\text{NH}$ proton. The seven aromatic protons in this compound resonated as a multiplet ca. δ 7.4-6.5. A doublet was discernible at δ 5.07 ($J=14$ Hz) assigned to one C-23' proton due to geminal coupling. Another doublet observed at δ 4.53 accounted for one proton ($J=10$ Hz) which was assigned to C-3 hydrogen attached to a hydroxyl group. On deuteration this collapsed to a singlet. Two methoxyls, one aromatic $-\text{OMe}$ and the other $-\text{COOCH}_3$, could be located at δ 3.79 and δ 3.73. In the mass spectrum of the compound the corresponding peaks containing the 'A' part of the molecule could be located at 16 higher mass unit.

Grandifolinediol, when reduced with NaBH_4 in MeOH , afforded vobtusine which proved that grandifolinediol must be a compound of the vobtusine pattern. The sequence of reactions of grandifoline (which has isovobtusine skeleton) to vobtusine could be explained (Scheme 1). Another interesting observation was made by heating grandifolinediol, when grandifoline was obtained as the sole product. This fact demonstrated that isovobtusine could be converted to vobtusine skeleton (which differs only at their C-14 configuration) by the action of acid. The reverse transformation was effected just by heating.

Definitive evidence of the structure of grandifoline was available from ^{13}C -NMR spectra.

Dihydrograndifoline, obtained by the NaBH_4 reduction of grandifoline, has been shown to be an isomer of vobtusine. Hence ^{13}C -NMR spectrum was used to solve the problem, which unambiguously had confirmed that dihydrograndifoline was identical with isovobtusine which differs in configuration from vobtusine at C-14. A comparison

SCHEME—1

 Transformation of Grandifoline to Grandifolindiol
 (Plausible Mechanism)

of the ^{13}C -NMR spectra of the reduction product of grandifoline (i.e., dihydrograndifoline) with that of vobtusine established the identity of the chiral centres on the periphery of the bases and revealed significant shift differences only at C-18 and ring D and F' carbons C-3, 14, 15, 16', 22' and 23'. Among these, only C-3 and C-23' had identical substituents, but could be differentiated by the Cotton-effect of the 2'-OH group on C-23'. Thus vobtusine and dihydrograndifoline differed only at C-14 and dihydrograndifoline was, in fact, nothing but C-14 stereomer of vobtusine.

^{13}C -NMR was useful in confirming the structure of grandifoline proposed earlier. The chemical tie-up of grandifoline with 14-isovobtusine by borohydride reduction and the liberation of a 2'-hydroxy group in this reaction indicated this tetracyclic

alkaloid (grandifoline) to be a didehydroisovobtusine whose C-2' oxygen was bridged to an amino carbon. In conformity with this view, the ^{13}C -NMR spectra of grandifoline differed from that of 14-isovobtusine ($\equiv$ dihydrograndifoline) primarily by the absence of one aminomethylene and the presence of a methine substituted by two heteroatoms. The spectra of D₁-14-isovobtusine ($\equiv$ D₁-dihydrograndifoline), prepared by reduction of grandifoline by NaBD₄, revealed the disappearance of the C-3 signal. All the chemical shifts of 14-isovobtusine and grandifoline are given in table 3. Thus from all the spectral and chemical studies the structure of grandifoline could be presented as (XV) without distinction of the stereochemistry at the C-3 centre.

The chemical shifts of rings A', B', C', D' and E' of the above structure were almost unaltered from the values of their 2'-OH counterpart of either normal or 14-iso series. However, introduction of the 3,2' ether bridge causes dramatic shift at many of the carbons of the remaining rings. The drastic shift perturbations of the rings C, D, E and the D-attached tetrahydrofuran cannot be accommodated by a H(3 β) configuration, since this stereochemistry, depicted in the following conformation, will affect the carbon chemical shifts of only C-3, 5, 14, 15 and 21. The shift alterations of the centres far removed from the ether-bridging site indicated that more deep-seated conformational changes must be involved in this situation. Thus it appears that grandifoline possesses α -configuration at C₃-H as illustrated in the above structure(XV).

Thus, the structure elucidation of grandifoline posed a challenging problem. This could be solved

TABLE 3—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF GRANDIFOLINE AND 14-ISOVOLTUSINE (NaBH₄ REDUCTION PRODUCT OF GRANDIFOLINE)

14-Isovoibtusine		Grandifoline	14-Isovoibtusine		Grandifoline
C-2	166.7	165.9	C-2'	94.4 ^a	94.6 ^b
C-3	58.0	91.9	C-3'	48.8	49.0
C-5	51.4		C-5'	52.0	53.2
C-6	44.4		C-6'	31.3	31.1
C-7	54.8	59.1	C-7'	56.4	54.4
C-8	137.9	137.1	C-8'	134.2	136.0
C-9	121.5	122.4	C-9'	113.5	114.6
C-10	120.5	120.9	C-10'	118.5	118.8
C-11	127.5	127.7	C-11'	110.3	111.1
C-12	109.1	109.0	C-12'	146.0	145.8
C-13	142.8	142.9	C-13'	136.8	136.2
C-14	38.9	38.1	C-14'	25.5	26.1
C-15	81.5	87.6	C-15'	80.4	80.9
C-16	94.3 ^a	92.8 ^b	C-16'	32.4 ^c	32.8
C-17	28.1		C-17'	32.6 ^c	34.4 ^d
C-18	63.7	67.2	C-18'	65.3	65.0
C-19	35.1		C-19'	36.8	35.8
C-20	47.9	49.9	C-20'	44.4	44.1
C-21	69.9	70.6	C-21'	63.7	65.8
C=O	168.1	168.1	C-22'	35.1	
OCH ₃	50.9	50.9	C-23'	46.5	
NCH ₃		49.0 ^e & 50.9	OCH ₃	50.0	55.6
CH ₃		34.0 ^d			
		38.1			
		38.6 & 41.5			

^a'-d' Signals may be reversed.
(TMS)=(CDCl₃)+76.9 ppm.

with the assistance of modern spectroscopy conjointly with chemical transformations. In conclusion I would like to emphasise that grandifoline is the only dimeric indole base of vobtusine series that is cleavable into its monomers.

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